

Democratising the cybersecurity protection process

We worked with a cybersecurity and threat intelligence platform which allowed their users to exponentially decrease the time taken to deploy protections against threats that are relevant to their organization and industry.

- UX Audit
- Task Flow Optimization
- Navigational structure Redesign
- Wireframing
- Visual Design

The Engagement

Strategic Changes for Immediate impact

- Rapid Evaluation of the current product and identification of improvements - near term and long term
- Optimization of Key workflows which resulted in: 40% Increase in efficiency

Fast go-to-market of Keystone features

No-code protection builder

Reduced the barrier of entry for SOC analysts by enabling them to build protections using a simple drag and drop interface without the need of knowledge of complex code paradigms

3x faster protection creation

25% Reduction in Error Rates

1 Click Protection

Alleviated anxiety in critical breach situations with 1 click protection deployment

5x Faster deployment

Co-Pilot

Enabled the product with AI which assisted in detection engineering tasks like –

- Explaining Events
- Writing Reports
- Assisting in hunts
- Building protections

Structural changes to the product for future proofing.

Created detailed story book components which improved consistency and reusability of component

300% Increased component coverage

Standardized design system which lead to code reusability

3x Faster FE implementation

Strategic code refactoring for more optimized performance

upto 30% Increased performance

Introduction of complex visualization capabilities which are completely customizable

Migrated the UI library from the existing MUI4 to MUI5

Source: <https://www.copods.co/case-studies/cybersecurity>